

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Mandelic Acid by Cerium(IV) Sulphate

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Kinetics of the oxidation of mandelic acid by Ce(IV) in sulphuric acid medium has been studied. The reactive species has been shown to be $Ce(SO_4)_2$. Activation parameters have been evaluated and mechanism proposed.

The kinetics of the oxidation of mandelic acid has been studied by Krishna and Tewari¹. The proposed $Ce(SO_4)_2$ to be reactive species, however, different reactive species i.e., $HCe(SO_4)_3^-$, $Ce(SO_4)^{2+}$ have been proposed by various workers¹⁻⁴ for the oxidation of L-hydroxyacids by Cerium(IV). The present study was undertaken to re-examine various claims.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals were of A.R. grade. Reaction was followed by usual titrimetric procedure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Product analysis : Oxidation of mandelic acid gave quantitative yield of benzaldehyde. As estimated using 2,4 dinitrophenylhydrazine, the order with respect to cerium (IV) and mandelic acid comes out to be one each.

Addition of bisulphate ion at constant H^+ ion concentration retards the reaction considerable (cf. Table 1). Table 2 records the results of effect of temperature on it.

Strict first order dependence of the rate rules out the formation of intermediate complex⁷ (cf. Bhargava, Joshi and Shanker²).

From kinetics point of view the real problem, in cerium oxidation is the multiplicity of cerium species, probably each one with its own characteristic rate constant. Using the value of equilibrium constants k_1 , k_2 and k_3 for the formation of various ceric sulphate complexes⁸ and the data of Table 1 one can calculate the rate of various cerium (IV) sulphate species. The order with respect to HSO_4^- (cf. Table 1) rules out Ce^+_{4} and $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$. The only species left in the present case are $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and $Ce(SO_4)^{2+}$. Assuming both of them to be reactive the following rate expression can be derived

$$\frac{k_1}{[M.A.]} = \frac{k'[H^+]^2}{k_2 k_3 [HSO_4^-]^{-2}} + \frac{k''[H^+]}{k_3 [HSO_4^-]} \quad (1)$$

where k' and k'' are the rate constant for the oxidation of mandelic acid by $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{+2}$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ respectively. At constant H^+ ion equation (1) reduces to

$$\frac{k_1[\text{HSO}_4^-]}{[\text{M.A.}]} = \frac{a}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]} + b$$

where $a = \frac{k'[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_2k_3}$ and $b = \frac{k''[\text{H}^+]}{k_3}$

k' and k'' have been evaluated (cf. Table 4) from the values of 'a' and 'b' determined using method of least square, from the data of Table 1. Table 4 shows that $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)^{+2}$ is not the reactive species in the oxidation of mandelic acid, by $\text{Ce}(\text{IV})$ as proposed by Krishna and Tewari.

TABLE 1

Effect of bisulphate ions on the reaction rate

[Ce(IV)] $4.4 \times 10^{-3}M$; [M.A.] $1.5 \times 10^{-2}M$; [H⁺] $1.4M$. Temp. 35°

[HSO ₄ ⁻] mol l ⁻¹	0.28	0.62	0.91	1.24	1.40
10^4k_1 (s ⁻¹)	58.00	47.60	36.20	28.30	25.60

TABLE 2

Effect of temperature on the reaction rate

[Ce(IV)] $5.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ [H₂SO₄] $1.40M$

Temp. °K	10^2k l mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	ΔE^* k cal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* e.u.
303	1.10	19.6 ± 1	-3.6
308	1.84		
313	3.04		
318	5.06		

TABLE 3

Concentration of Ce(IV) species

[H⁺] $1.4M$

Species	[HSO ₄ ⁻] = $1.4M$	[HSO ₄ ⁻] $0.28M$
[Ce ⁺⁴]	6.8×10^{-8} [Ce(IV)]	7.1×10^{-5} [Ce(IV)]
[Ce(SO ₄) ⁺²]	2.4×10^{-4} [Ce(IV)]	5.0×10^{-3} [Ce(IV)]
[Ce(SO ₄) ₂]	4.7×10^{-2} [Ce(IV)]	0.20 [Ce(IV)]
[Ce(SO ₄) ₃ ⁻²]	0.95 [Ce(IV)]	0.80 [Ce(IV)]

TABLE 4

Rate constant for Ce(IV) species
 $[\text{HSO}_4^-] 0.28M; [\text{H}^+] 1.4M; \text{Temp. } 35^\circ$

<i>a</i>	<i>k'</i> 1.mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	<i>b</i>	<i>k''</i> 1.mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
—	—	0.28	39.2×10^{-2}

Kemp and Waters⁹ suggested, on the basis of primary isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 1.22$), that in the oxidation of mandelic acid C-H bond rupture played a minor part. Further, the activation parameters^{10,11}, also suggest a C-C bond fission. Thus the following mechanism may be proposed

where Ce(IV) represents Ce(SO₄)₂.

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